

Correlation Analysis of Matooke Instrumental Measurements and Sensory Panel Data

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Kephas NOWAKUNDA, NARL, Kampala, Uganda

Elizabeth KHAKASA, NARL, Kampala, Uganda

Moreen ASASIRA, NARL, Kampala, Uganda

Sarah KISAKYE, NARL, Kampala, Uganda

Mary Gorreth NAMUDDU, NARL, Kampala, Uganda

Living TUKASHABA, NARL, Kampala, Uganda

Amos ASIIMWE, NARL, Kampala, Uganda

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Ethics: The activities, which led to the production of this document, were assessed and approved by the CIRAD Ethics Committee (H2020 ethics self-assessment procedure). When relevant, samples were prepared according to good hygiene and manufacturing practices. When external participants were involved in an activity, they were priorly informed about the objective of the activity and explained that their participation was entirely voluntary, that they could stop the interview at any point and that their responses would be anonymous and securely stored by the research team for research purposes.

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This document has been reviewed by	
Oluwatoyin AYETIGBO, CIRAD	20/03/2025
Santiago ARUFE, CIRAD	20/03/2025
Final validation by	
Eglantine FAUVELLE, CIRAD	25/03/2025

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ACRONYMS

JAR Just About Right

NARL National Agricultural Research Laboratories

RTB Root, Tubers and Bananas

SOP Standard Operating Procedures

TPA Textural Profile Analysis

QDA Quantitative Descriptive Analysis

WP Work package

ABSTRACT

This report presents the results of a correlation study of instrumental texture, colour, quantitative descriptive analysis (QDA) and consumer test data of 10 contrasting genotypes.

The objective of this activity was to confirm how dependable the instrumental measures of matooke colour and texture are in predicting the sensory quality of matooke vis-à-vis colour and texture, respectively.

Ten contrasting genotypes including landraces (Kibuzi, Mbwazirume, Nakitembe, Nfuuka) and hybrids (NARITA 17, M30, M9, NARITA 9, NARITA 13, and NARITA 22) were used in the study. The genotypes were cooked (Nowakunda et al. 2019) and divided into three portions (1) For consumer testing (Marimo et al, 2019); (2) For QDA analysis (Khakasa et al. 2023), and (3) for texture and colour instrumental analyses (Nowakunda et al. 2023; Khakasa et al, 2024). Correlation analyses were performed using means, and ANOVAs in XLSTAT.

Results showed positive correlation ($r = 0.78$) between the instrumentally assessed yellowness (b^* cooked pulp) and Sensorial assessed yellowness. The instrumental yellowness (b^* cooked pulp) and overall liking score for the colour of the cooked matooke was also positively related ($r = 0.81$). However, the yellowness of the raw matooke pulp (b^* raw pulp) had a moderate positive correlation ($r = 0.59$) with the yellowness of the cooked pulp (b^* cooked pulp). For texture, strong positive correlation was observed between firmness in the mouth and instrumental hardness ($r = 0.97$) implying that firmer samples are perceived as hard. Positive correlations were observed between moistness and smoothness (0.84), smoothness and overall liking (0.87); implying that consumers prefer matooke samples that are smooth and moist.

Key Words: Matooke, Quality traits, correlation, instrumental, Color, Texture

1. INTRODUCTION

The work presented in this report covers activities conducted under RTB breeding for quality. In phase I, correlation of the laboratory, instrumental colour, texture, quantitative descriptive analysis (QDA), and consumer preferences of four advanced genotypes revealed promising potential to predict consumer characteristics using quantitative assessments. Also, standard operating protocols (SOPs) for sensory, colour and texture analysis were developed (doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00593, <https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00782>, <https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00602>). During phase 2, more experiments were conducted in order to confirm the correlations between instrumental texture, sensory and consumer preferences for key traits. In these experiments, instrumental color, texture, QDA and consumer preference data were generated on 10 contrasting genotypes (good, medium and bad). The generated data were correlated to confirm the dependability of the instrument generated data in predicting consumer preferences when used in screening.

2. METHODOLOGY

Guided by previous data from descriptive sensory analysis conducted during the RTBFoods, 10 contrasting genotypes were selected. They included four local varieties; Kibuzi, Mbwazirume, Nakitembe, and Nfuuka; and six hybrids; NARITA 17, M30, M9, NARITA 9, NARITA 13, and NARITA 22. The selected genotypes were sourced from breeding fields and harvested at mature green stage. The varieties were prepared (Nowakunda et al. 2019) and divided into three portions (1) For consumer testing (Marimo et al, 2019); (2) For QDA analysis (Khakasa et al. 2023), and (3) for texture and colour instrumental analyses (Nowakunda et al. 2023; Khakasa et al, 2024) .

3. RESULTS

3.1 Correlations between sensory and instrumental colour parameters of matooke

Table 1 below shows the Pearson's correlation matrix between sensory and instrumental colour parameters. The results showed positive correlation ($r=0.98$) between yellowness and Overall Liking. Also, a positive correlation ($r=0.71$) between yellowness and homogeneity of colour, homogeneity of the colour and overall Liking ($r=0.71$), suggesting that more yellow matooke also tends to have a uniform colour and this also is reflected in consumer preference.

Table 1: Pearson's correlation matrix showing relationships between QDA, overall liking, and instrumental colour parameters

Variables	Yellow	Homogeneity of colour	of Overall liking	L*rawpulp	b*rawpulp	L*cookedpulp	b*cookedpulp
Yellow	1	0.71	0.98	-0.28	-0.01	-0.11	0.78
Homogeneity of colour	0.71	1	0.71	0.11	0.07	0.33	0.29
Overall liking for colour	0.98	0.71	1	-0.16	0.09	-0.01	0.81
L*rawpulp	-0.28	0.11	-0.16	1	0.77	0.50	0.34
b*rawpulp	-0.01	0.07	0.09	0.77	1	0.67	0.59
L*cookedpulp	-0.11	0.33	-0.01	0.50	0.67	1	0.48
b*cookedpulp	0.78	0.29	0.81	0.34	0.59	0.48	1

Values in bold are different from 0 with a significance level $\alpha=0.05$

The results also showed positive correlation ($r=0.78$) between the instrumentally assessed yellowness (b*cooked pulp) and sensorial assessed yellowness. Also, the correlation between the instrumental yellowness (b* cooked pulp) and overall liking score for the colour of the cooked matooke was positive ($r=0.81$). However, the yellowness of the raw matooke pulp (b*raw pulp) had a moderate positive correlation ($r=0.59$) with the yellowness of the cooked pulp (bcooked pulp). The results confirmed earlier observations which revealed the yellowness in raw matooke may not be a reliable predictor of yellowness of cooked matooke. Only the instrumental colour assessments on the cooked pulp was dependable in predicting acceptable colour of cooked matooke.

3.2 Correlations between sensory and instrumental colour parameters of matooke

Table 2 below shows a Pearson's correlation matrix between QDA, consumer preference, and TPA texture parameters. The results showed a strong negative correlation between firmness and moistness (-0.96). As moistness increases, firmness decreases, suggesting that moistness contributes to softer samples. Also, a strong positive correlation was observed between firmness in the mouth and instrumental hardness (0.97) implying that firmer samples are perceived as hard (Table 2).

Strong positive correlations were observed between moistness and smoothness (0.84), smoothness and overall liking (0.87); implying that consumers prefer matooke samples that are smooth and moist (Table 2).

On the other hand, a moderate negative correlation was observed between instrumental hardness and overall liking (-0.54) suggesting that as hardness increases, overall liking decreases, which implies that harder samples are less preferred (Table 2). Similarly, a moderate negative correlation was also observed between stickiness and Overall Liking (-0.53). Matooke that is stickier tends to be less liked implying that excessive stickiness negatively affects consumer preference.

Table 2: Correlation matrix (Pearson) showing relationships between QDA textural parameters, consumer preference, and TPA parameters

Variables	Firmness M	Moisture M	Smoothness M	hardness T	Moldability T	Stickiness T	Overall liking	Raw Pulp (N)	TPA Hardness	Cohesiveness	Adhesiveness
Firmness M	1	-0.96	-0.79	0.96	-0.75	-0.09	-0.49	0.23	0.40	-0.71	0.43
Moisture M	-0.96	1	0.84	-0.96	0.83	0.18	0.53	-0.3	-0.32	0.76	-0.42
Smoothness M	-0.79	0.84	1	-0.85	0.91	-0.30	0.87	-0.15	-0.15	0.55	-0.23
hardness T	0.97	-0.96	-0.85	1	-0.80	-0.05	-0.54	0.18	0.32	-0.66	0.35
Moldability T	-0.75	0.83	0.91	-0.80	1	-0.09	0.84	-0.05	-0.08	0.63	-0.23
Stickiness T	-0.09	0.18	-0.30	-0.05	-0.09	1	-0.53	-0.29	-0.18	0.21	-0.13
Overall liking	-0.49	0.53	0.87	-0.54	0.84	-0.53	1	0.13	-0.04	0.27	-0.05
Raw Pulp (N)	0.23	-0.33	-0.15	0.18	-0.05	-0.29	0.13	1	-0.13	-0.43	0.76
TPA Hardness	0.40	-0.32	-0.15	0.32	-0.08	-0.18	-0.04	-0.13	1	0.05	-0.06
Cohesiveness	-0.71	0.76	0.55	-0.66	0.63	0.21	0.27	-0.43	0.05	1	-0.55
Adhesiveness	0.43	-0.42	-0.23	0.35	-0.23	-0.13	-0.05	0.76	-0.06	-0.55	1

M = In the mouth, T = in the hands

There was a strong positive correlation between moldability and overall liking (0.84). Samples that are more moldable tend to be liked more, indicating that consumers prefer textures that can easily deform rather than stiff, rigid textures.

3.3 Discriminant Analysis for texture of the matooke genotypes

All the TPA textural parameters were discriminant among the matooke genotypes. The most significant textural parameters are springiness and gumminess of cooked matooke. The chewiness is the least discriminant textural property. The landrace Mbwarzirume has low hardness, gumminess and chewiness, and has intermediate adhesiveness, cohesiveness, springiness and resilience that is characteristic of texture of a pasty, slightly soft, inhomogeneous swallow food that matooke is known for (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Discriminant analysis for texture of the matooke genotypes

The clustering of cooked matooke genotypes based on TPA texture showed that NFUUKA was clustered separate from other genotypes having the highest level of hardness, gumminess, chewiness and

adhesiveness. Kibuzi, NARITA 13, M9 and NARITA 17 were clustered together and had the lowest level of hardness and adhesiveness, but higher levels of cohesiveness and springiness. Genotypes M30, NARITA 9, NARITA 22, Mbwazirume and Nakitembe were clustered together with intermediate texture.

CONCLUSION

The results confirmed strong correlations between instrumentally and sensorial assessed parameters of matooke colour and texture. TPA and Chroma could therefore be useful medium throughput tools to screen the often-large numbers of matooke hybrids for the two traits. Colour and Textural profiles are top key traits that drive preference in matooke. Previous studies have shown that no matooke hybrids can be adopted by farmers and other end-users if they do not have acceptable intensities of yellow colour and textural profiles (softness, smoothness both in hand and mouth).

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